

Large-area superhydrophobic nanofiber array structures for drag reduction

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SUMMARY

We first report large-area superhydrophobic nanostructures with flexibility, cost-effective and drag reduction by adopting curing process, which have uniform superhydrophobicity on the size of $30 \times 14 \text{ cm}^2$. Such nanostructures could be a potential platform for many applications such as microfluidic devices for biological studies, and industrial self-cleaning products for automobiles and ships.

Keywords: Superhydrophobicity, Drag reduction, Nanohoneycomb, Anodic aluminium oxide, wettability

INTRODUCTION

Surface with a static contact angle (CA) greater than 150° are in general defined as superhydrophobic surfaces. Superhydrophobic surface have great potentials in fundamental research,[1-5] and also wide practical applications in the production of textile, microfluidics, self-cleaning surfaces, building glass, windshields of cars, ships hulls, pipes and the satellite antenna surfaces.[6] Superhydrophobic surfaces can be produced in two ways: The first is to create a rough surface, and the second is to modify the surface using materials with low surface free energy.[1,5,7] Hydrophobicity is usually enhanced by surface roughness, especially by fractal structures using techniques such as self-assembly of a monolayer, photolithography, plasma polymerization, UV illumination, polymer coating, electrospinning, ion irradiation and the template method.[2,3,5,7-12]

Unfortunately these methods involve expensive materials with complex time-consuming processes and they are limited by size (e.g., wafer) and also the resulting surface degrades with age in air. It is therefore important to develop a simple fabrication method for the flexible large-sized area having a uniform superhydrophobicity with durability in air and water.

Anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) has recently been proposed as a material suitable for use in nanotechnology. Porous type AAO has the attractive feature of allowing simple control of pore dimensions, diameter, pore length and density by varying the anodizing conditions [13-14]. The pore radius and the interpore distance depend on the immersion

time in electrolyte solution and the anodic voltage. The superhydrophobic surface was fabricated by replication of the porous AAO nanohoneycomb template.

We report below flexible superhydrophobic nanofiber array structures with tens of centimeter scale achieved using a replicating and curing method, which are unaffected by aging in air and water with drag reduction effect, using industrial aluminum (99.5%). This process has the major advantages over conventional methods of convenience, low cost and stability over time. The resulting nanostructure has potential to be deployed in diverse applications such as microfluidic devices for biological studies and industrial self-cleaning products for automobiles, ships, and houses.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The fabrication process of large-area superhydrophobic nanofiber array structures is shown schematically in Figure 1. First, nanoporous AAO nanohoneycomb was fabricated by anodization of industrial Al (99.5% 1000 time cheaper than 99.999% Al, 300 mm × 140 mm × 0.1 mm) foil using oxalic acid. To generate nanostructures on an industrial Al surface, anodization was performed on an industrial Al foil for 8h in 0.3M oxalic solution at a constant voltage of 40V, using a computer power supply (Digital Electronics Co., DRP-92001DUS). The solution was maintained at a temperature of 15 °C during anodization by a circulator (Lab. Companion, RW-0525G). Conventional superhydrophobic surface using anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) template have been fabricated by anodizing pure aluminum (99.999%). [11] It is not necessary to achieve a regular pore arrangement for the AAO nanohoneycomb template, however, so the AAO nanohoneycomb template is fabricated using industrial aluminum foil.

A replication template with widened nano-hole size was fabricated by immersing AAO nanohoneycomb template in a phosphoric acid solution. The pores were widened by immersing the nanoporous AAO nanohoneycomb in 0.1M phosphoric acid solution at 25 °C for 45 min. (The widening times are respectively 0 and 45 min, as shown in Figs. 2a,b) The widened specimens were washed with distilled water and the surface was air-dried at room temperature.

The nanoporous AAO nanohoneycomb prepared by the above process is used as replication template. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, Teflon® AF 601S2, 6 wt%, Dupont™) solution is rubbed onto the replication template and curing was carried out at room temperature for one day. To fabricate a large-area superhydrophobic surface, it is necessary to use polyimide tape (GA-1803: Dashyun ST) to maintain a PTFE thin film because the film is unable to be maintained over a large-area. Polyimide tape is made of polyimide film coated with silicone adhesive and primer. The specimen is cured in a forced convection oven (JEIO TECH, OF-02GW) at 120 °C for 5h, yielding strong attachment between the PTFE film and polyimide tape, because of a crosslinked silicone adhesive and primer. [15] If curing process is not performed, the PTFE film will be detached from polyimide because of acid solution and reaction heat, which have partial superhydrophobicity. [12] The nanofiber array structure, designed to have high aspect ratio, resulted following the removal of nanoporous AAO nanohoneycomb with AZ300MIF developer at room temperature.

The water contact angles of the nanofiber array structures were measured using a Drop shape Analysis system (DSA-100, Kruss Co.) at room temperature. Mean water contact angles were obtained by measuring the same sample at ten different positions. Topography of the nanofiber array structures was characterized using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM; JEOL JSM-7401F, NCNT).

To investigate aging in air, contact angles were measured monthly while the specimen was maintained at room temperature. For water aging, specimens were maintained in water at 15 °C and were pulled out monthly for contact angle measurement (water depth is about 50 mm).

The Hydrophobic forces acting on the test plates were measured using a 3-component load-cell (Nissho LMS-3502) having non-linearity less than $\pm 0.5\%$ over the full range of 2kgf. The load-cell has temperature sensitivity $0.05\%/C^\circ$ when it is coupled with a DC strain amplifier. The precision error was found to be less than 3%. The drag coefficient, based on the bottom area (A) of the flat plate, is defined as follows:

$$C_D = \frac{Drag}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_0^2 A} \quad (1)$$

where ρ and U_0 respectively denote the density of water and free stream velocity. Drag measurements were carried out for 3 flat plates (Al, specimen 1-2). Each plate was $300 \times 140 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$ in size. The drag force acting in the streamwise direction on the test plates was measured.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The surface morphologies of the AAO nanohoneycomb templates were investigated by scanning electron microscopy, as shown in figures 2a,b. The mean pore diameters of the AAO nanohoneycomb without the widening process are about 20-30 nm, and the mean pore diameters with widening are about 50-60 nm. The mean pore size is dependent on the immersion time in 0.1M phosphoric acid solution at 25 °C, the simple control of the mean pore size in fabrication is highly significant. The nanoporous AAO have an irregular array and varying pore diameter, because of the use of industrial Al. Since the aluminium foil was anodized for 8h, the two specimens have the pore depth about 48 μm . [14] The nanoporous AAO nanohoneycomb have giant mean aspect ratios (870-1920).

The nanofiber array structures were obtained after removal of AAO template. Figures 2c,d are SEM images of the structures, after widening times of 0 min (specimen 1) and 45 min (specimen 2). The structures have high mean aspect ratios (1920 and 870, respectively), showing the dominant effect of the nanofiber sticking phenomenon. The nanofibers used to perform the widening process are thicker and denser.

The superhydrophobic property of nanofiber array structures was investigated by measuring contact angles of water droplet; the resulting static and dynamic contact angles are shown in Table 1 and figure 2e,f. The nanofiber array structures contain trapped air which reduces the actual contact area between the surface and water droplet, so that the structures exhibit strongly superhydrophobicity. The nanofiber array structures which had undergone the widening process have mean edge to edge spacing

of the nanofibers smaller than without widening. The air-filled space of specimen 2 is smaller, and it gives a smaller difference between the advancing and receding angle (hysteresis), so that it provide a more robust Cassie state than the other surface. Figure 2g,h shows large areas of uniformly superhydrophobic surface, with fields of view of $300\text{ mm} \times 140\text{ mm}$ and flexibility.

Figure 3a shows the variation of drag coefficients with Reynolds number, based on the length of the test plate. Specimen 2 has a smaller drag coefficient than the others. The drag reduction of specimen 2 is 22.5% ~ 28.5% in the range of Reynolds numbers tested, as shown in figure 3(a) inset, being unaffected by aging in figure 3b. Although specimen 1 exhibits superhydrophobicity, which corresponds to a low value of contact angle hysteresis, and this specimen has more air filled space than specimen 2, there is no drag reduction effect. This is probably due to the external pressure (as a result of the flow velocity, flux and hydrostatic) that can cause to intrude into the air filled space between the nanofiber. [4] As the air-filled space of specimen 1 becomes filled with water, it loses its water repellent properties. (The CA after drag measurement are shown in Table 1)

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have successfully fabricated large-area uniform superhydrophobic nanofiber array structure by curing process. Furthermore, the widened nanofiber array structures maintain superhydrophobicity even after storage in air or water for three months, confirming that these structures are stable and reliable. Such a nanofiber array structures could be a potential platform for many applications such as microfluidic devices for biological studies, and industrial self-cleaning products for automobiles, ship and house.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic diagram of the process for fabrication of nanofiber array structures using industrial aluminum foil. By curing process, it enhances attachment strength between the PTFE film and polyimide tape, because of a crosslinked silicone adhesive and primer.

Figure 2. SEM images of [(a) and (b)] nanoporous AAO (widening, 0 and 45 min); [(c) and (d)] nanofiber array structures (widening, 0 and 45 min). Water droplet and contact angle of [(e) and (f)] nanofiber array structures (widening, 0 and 45 min). (g) A virtually ball-shaped water droplet on a large-area superhydrophobic nanofiber array structures (widening time of 45 min). (h) Image of tens of centimeter scale flexible nanofiber array structure with uniform superhydrophobicity.

Figure 3. (a) Comparison of drag coefficient variation. The inset shows the drag reduction rate for Reynolds numbers. The drag reduction rate of widened nanofiber array structures is 22.5~28.5% in the range of Reynolds numbers tested. (b) Aging effect in air and water on contact angle of the nanofiber array structures (widening time of 45 min). The nanofiber array structures are unaffected aging in air or water

Table 1. Static and dynamic water contact angles of the nanofiber array structures after widening for 45 min, in comparison to the NFAS using nanoporous AAO without widening.

	Widening time: 0 min (specimen 1)	Widening time: 45 min (specimen 2)
Static CA [deg]	163.0	168.0
Advancing CA [deg]	163.0	168.0
Receding CA [deg]	159.0	166.5
CA hysteresis [deg]	4.0	1.5
Static CA after drag measurement [deg]	11.0	167.0

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